

Techno-Economic Analysis for Partial Substitution of Diesel by Renewable Hydrogen in Haulage Mining Trucks

Daniel Cavadía Suárez^{1*}

¹*Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Universidad de La Guajira, Km 5 vía Maicao, Riohacha, 440001, Colombia*

*Corresponding author: dcavadia93@gmail.com

Abstract

The mining industry has a high demand for fossil fuels, which has led to increased environmental challenges. Therefore, there is a need to find cleaner and more sustainable energy sources. Renewable hydrogen is an alternative being explored to make mining more sustainable. This study aims to evaluate the feasibility of partially replacing diesel with renewable hydrogen in mining trucks. The technical analysis involved studying the production of hydrogen using models of a solar photovoltaic system coupled with a proton exchange membrane electrolyzer. The compressed hydrogen was then supplied to the mining truck. The economic analysis evaluated the feasibility by calculating the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) and the cost of on-board hydrogen (COOBH) of the mining truck. These were then compared with diesel price scenarios. The study estimated an LCOH of 6.2 USD/kgH₂, which is a plausible value compared to literature data. However, the COOBH of 10.29 USD/kgH₂ is considered significantly high compared to international diesel price scenarios. It is expected that technological advancements and possible improvements in hydrogen production processes will make it possible to generate hydrogen at much lower costs in the future. With these advancements, hydrogen will compete with liquid fossil fuels in a sustainable and economically viable way. This will pave the way for a more effective transition towards cleaner energy sources in the mining industry.

Keywords: Mining trucks, sustainable energy, renewable hydrogen, electrolysis, photovoltaic system.

Nomenclature

Roman symbols

T_e	Ambient temperature	°C - K
t	Autonomy time of battery system	h
C_a	Battery capacity	%
V_{bat}	Battery voltage	V

k	Clearness index	
FC_i	Consumption factor for a mining truck	gal/h
$I_{mp,ref}$	Current at maximum power	A
C_1	Current constant 1 of PV module	
C_2	Current constant 2 of PV module	
P_d	Depth of discharge	%
FC	Diesel consumption factor	gal/h
LHV_{diesel}	Diesel lower heating value	MJ/kg
f	Diffuse fraction	
$G_{d,h}$	Diffuse horizontal solar radiation	W/m ²
$G_{d,\beta}$	Diffuse radiation component	W/m ²
$G_{b,\beta}$	Direct radiation	W/m ²
i	Discount rate	%
I	Electrolyzer current	A
S_i	Energetic amount of diesel to replace	MJ
M_t	Energy generation in one year	kWh
M_{H2i}	Equivalent amount of hydrogen	kg
t_{eq}	Equivalent time	
G_{0h}	Extraterrestrial horizontal radiation	W/m ²
F	Faraday constant	C/mol
G_h	Global horizontal solar radiation	W/m ²
h_{in}	Hydrogen enthalpy at the cooling inlet	kJ/kg
h_{out}	Hydrogen enthalpy at the cooling outlet	kJ/kg
LHV_{H2}	Hydrogen lower heating value	MJ/kg
\dot{m}_{H_2}	Hydrogen mass flow	kg/h
\dot{n}_{H_2}	Hydrogen molar flow	kmol/h
\dot{V}_{H_2}	Hydrogen volumetric flow	m ³ /h
I_0	Initial investment cost (PV system)	USD
C_T	Installation cost	USD
E_i	Mining truck energy consumption	MJ
F	Modulation function (F factor)	
P	Nominal power	W
N_{bat}	Number of batteries for a bank	
z	Number of electrons	
A_t	Operating cost (PV system)	USD
$C_{O\&M}$	Operation and maintenance cost	USD
\dot{m}_{O_2}	Oxygen mass flow	kg/h
\dot{n}_{O_2}	Oxygen molar flow	kmol/h
\dot{V}_{O_2}	Oxygen volumetric flow	m ³ /h
$\%S$	Partial Substitution percentage	%
ΔT	PV module temperature variation	°C
P_{pv}	PV panel power	W
V_{pv}	PV panel voltage	V

P_i	Rated power of a mining truck	kW
$V_{oc,ref}$	Reference open circuit voltage	V
G_{ref}	Reference solar radiation	W/m ²
$G_{r,\beta}$	Reflected radiation component	W/m ²
C_{REP}	Replacement cost	USD
$I_{sc,ref}$	Short-circuit current	A
I_{pv}	Solar module current	A
t_s	Standard time	
P_{system}	System power	W
G_β	Total solar radiation	W/m ²
R	Universal ideal gas constant	kJ/kmol.K
ΔI	PV current variation	A
$V_{mp,ref}$	Voltage at maximum power	V
\dot{m}_{H_2O}	Water mass flow	kg/h
\dot{n}_{H_2O}	Water molar flow	kmol/h
M_{H_2O}	Water molar mass	kg/kmol
\dot{V}_{H_2O}	Water volumetric flow	m ³ /h

Abbreviations

<i>CNG</i>	Compressed natural gas	
<i>COOBH</i>	Cost of onboard hydrogen	USD/kg
<i>FLH</i>	Full load hours	h
<i>HDCNG</i>	High-density compressed natural gas	
<i>LCOE</i>	Levelized cost of energy	USD/kWh
<i>LCOH</i>	Levelized cost of hydrogen	USD/kg
<i>NPC</i>	Net present cost	USD
<i>NOCT</i>	Nominal operating cell temperature	°C

Greek symbols

β	Angle of the surface inclined towards the equator	°
η_f	Faraday efficiency	
ω	Hour angle	°
ρ_{H_2}	Hydrogen density	kg/m ³
θ	Incidence angle	°
ρ_{O_2}	Oxygen density	kg/m ³
δ	Solar declination	°
μ_{Isc}	Temperature coefficient of I_{sc}	%/°C
μ_{Voc}	Temperature coefficient of V_{oc}	%/°C
ρ_{H_2O}	Water density	kg/m ³

1. Introduction

Diesel consumption by haulage trucks in the mining industry is a significant component of operating costs, representing up to 32% of the total energy input [1]. Additionally, this consumption poses environmental challenges due to the associated emissions, which contribute significantly to air pollution and climate change. This study evaluates the feasibility of partially substituting diesel with renewable hydrogen in haulage mining trucks. We developed models using on-site solar photovoltaic (PV) energy, direct coupling of the PV generator with a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer, compressed storage, and supply to the mining truck. We also estimated the levelized cost of energy (LCOE), the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH), and the cost of on-board hydrogen (COOBH).

Many countries have strengthened green mining by implementing strategies to replace fossil fuels by incorporating renewable energy. These efforts aim to mitigate the influence of volatility in the prices of such fuels and advance in decarbonization. The main solutions focus on the technological conversion of transport trucks focused on the replacement of fossil fuels in electric mode with electricity generated by photovoltaic energy or wind [2] and, on the other hand, the use of hydrogen through fuel cells of proton exchange membrane (PEMFC) for clean propulsion and which are based on their ability to generate zero emissions [3]. Renewable hydrogen is also considered a viable approach for this type of truck since it can effectively replace diesel as a fuel [4], [5].

The connection between renewable hydrogen and green mining could be beneficial not only from an energy or environmental point of view but also from an economic point of view to reduce operating costs in the long term, given that these projects have proven to be competitively viable. in the energy market[6]. Al-Ghussain et al. [7] carried out a techno-economic feasibility study for a hybrid photovoltaic-wind system with energy accumulation aimed at the production of renewable hydrogen and thermal energy accumulation, concluding that at a maximum plant capacity of 194 GW, the levelized cost of green hydrogen is 1.42 USD/kgH₂. Lumbers et al. [8] carried out a techno-economic evaluation to study the viability of green hydrogen for decarbonization in an iron mine in Western Australia, obtaining as a result that the levelized cost of this hydrogen is 6.16 USD/kgH₂.

Incorporating hydrogen in diesel engines entails multiple technical advantages regarding performance, combustion, and other parameters inherent to said engines. Adding hydrogen could increase brake thermal efficiency (BTE) because hydrogen has a higher flame temperature and a higher flame speed that is approximately nine times faster than unblended diesel [9]. Deb et al. [10], analyzed a four-cylinder diesel engine operating in dual diesel-hydrogen mode, concluding that the inclusion of hydrogen generated notable improvements in the BTE, presenting an improvement of 3.9% in thermal efficiency when 11% of hydrogen was added. 4.9% when 17% hydrogen was added. The pressure inside the cylinder also has a significant impact. After all, instantaneous combustion occurs at a constant volume [9]. Dimitriou et al. [11] found in their analysis of a four-cylinder engine with 20 kW power that hydrogen addition rates between 40% and 90% generate pressure increases due to the early start of combustion. On the other hand, it has also been found that the use of hydrogen generates an increase in the heat release rate in the premixed combustion stage thanks to improved combustion efficiency. This is possible because hydrogen could be burned immediately by

propagating multiple turbulent flames generated by diesel combustion. Still, there may be a reduction in the diesel fuel burned about that injected, which can cause incomplete consumption [9].

Numerous studies have addressed hydrogen production from renewable sources. However, in the context of haulage mining trucks, there is a lack of techno-economic analysis on the partial replacement of diesel by renewable hydrogen. The present work is structured as follows: section 2 describes the models employed in the techno-economic analysis of the partial substitution of diesel by renewable hydrogen. Section 3 summarizes the results obtained and discusses the levelized costs of hydrogen, the hydrogen placed on the mining truck, and the comparative evaluation of the international diesel price. Finally, section 5 presents the conclusions of the document.

2. Renewable hydrogen production modeling and techno-economic analysis

2.1 Modeling of PV-Electrolyzer system

This study considers the geographic mining area of an open-pit coal mine. We used input data such as horizontal solar radiation and ambient temperature from the PVGIS database to determine solar radiation [12], [13]. Equation (1) gives the total solar radiation on an inclined surface (G_β) [14], [15], [16].

$$G_\beta = G_{b,\beta} + G_{r,\beta} + G_{d,\beta} \quad (1)$$

where $G_{b,\beta}$ is the direct radiation on the surface, $G_{r,\beta}$ is the reflected radiation, and $G_{d,\beta}$ the diffuse radiation. Equation (2) gives the direct radiation ($G_{b,\beta}$) [14], [15], [16].

$$G_{b,\beta} = (G_h - G_{d,h}) * \frac{\cos \theta}{\cos \theta_z} \quad (2)$$

where G_h is the global horizontal solar radiation retrieved from [12], $G_{d,h}$ is the diffuse horizontal solar radiation, θ is the sun angle of incidence, and θ_z is the zenith angle. Equation (3) gives the diffuse horizontal solar radiation ($G_{d,h}$).

$$G_{d,h} = f * G_h \quad (3)$$

where f corresponds to the fuzzy fraction, determined via Equation (4).

$$f = \begin{cases} 0.995 - 0.081k, & k \leq 0.21 \\ 0.724 + 2.738k - 8.32k^2 + 4.967k^3, & 0.21 < k \leq 0.76 \\ 0.18, & k > 0.76 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where k is the clarity index, given by Equation (5):

$$k = \frac{G_h}{G_{0h}} \quad (5)$$

where G_{0h} corresponds to the extraterrestrial horizontal radiation, given by Equation (6).

$$G_{0h} = \beta_0 * (\cos \theta_z) \left[1 + 0.033 \cos \left(\frac{d_n * 360^\circ}{365} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

where β_0 is the solar constant, which amounts to 1367 W/m², and d_n is the day number ranging from 1 to 365. Equation (7) gives the cosine value of the zenith angle (θ_z).

$$\cos \theta_z = \sin \delta \sin \varphi + \cos \delta \cos \varphi \cos \omega \quad (7)$$

where δ corresponds to the solar declination, φ corresponds to the latitude of the place (11.145° for Cerrejón), and ω is the hour angle. Equation (8) gives the solar declination.

$$\delta = 23.45^\circ * \sin \left[\frac{(d_n + 284) * 360^\circ}{365} \right] \quad (8)$$

The range of declination remains between $-23.45^\circ \leq \delta \leq 23.45^\circ$. Equation (9) gives the hour angle (ω).

$$\omega = 15 * (t_s - 12) \quad (9)$$

where t_s is called standard time, given by Equation (10).

$$t_s = t_{ct} + t_{eq} + \frac{L_{sd} - L}{15} \quad (10)$$

where t_{ct} corresponds to the local time, L is longitude (-72.618° for Cerrejón), L_{sd} is the standard longitude (meridian -74° for Colombia), and t_{eq} corresponds to the equivalent time, given by Equation (11).

$$t_{eq} = 229.2 [0.000075 + 0.001868 \cos \Gamma - 0.032077 \sin \Gamma - 0.014615 \cos(2\Gamma) - 0.04089 \sin(2\Gamma)] / 60$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{(d_n - 1) * 360^\circ}{365} \quad (11)$$

Equation 12 gives the cosine of the angle of incidence of the sun's rays (θ).

$$\cos \theta = \sin \delta \sin(\varphi - \beta) + \cos \delta \cos(\varphi - \beta) \cos \omega \quad (12)$$

where β corresponds to the angle of inclination of the surface towards the equator, given by Equation (13).

$$\beta = 0.69|\varphi| + 3.7 \quad (13)$$

where φ corresponds to the latitude of the place as previously defined. Equation (14) gives the reflected radiation component ($G_{r\beta}$).

$$G_{r,\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \rho G_h (1 - \cos \beta) \quad (18)$$

where ρ is the value of the albedo taken as 0.2, G_h is the experimentally measured horizontal global radiation, and β is the inclination angle. On the other hand, the diffuse radiation component ($G_{d,\beta}$) is determined by Equation (15).

$$G_{d,\beta} = G_{d,h} \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos \beta) \right] \left[1 + F \sin^3 \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) \right] (1 + F \cos^2 \theta \sin^3 \theta_z) \quad (15)$$

where F is the modulation factor given by Equation (16).

$$F = 1 - f^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{G_{d,h}}{G_h} \right)^2 \quad (16)$$

where f is the diffuse fraction mentioned above. Solar radiation modeling becomes the input information for estimating the instantaneous power generated by a photovoltaic panel. We used technical data of a monocrystalline panel TITAN RSM 120-8-600M, from its specification sheet and the equations denoted below, according to Ghribi [14]. Equation (17) gives the current intensity produced by the photovoltaic panel (I_{pv}).

$$I_{pv} = I_{sc,ref} \left\{ 1 - C_1 \left[\exp \left(\frac{V_{pv}}{C_2 * V_{oc,ref}} \right) - 1 \right] \right\} + \Delta I \quad (17)$$

where V_{pv} corresponds to the voltage produced by the panel, calculated using Equation (18).

$$V_{pv} = V_{mp,ref} \left[1 + 0.0539 \ln \left(\frac{G_\beta}{G_{ref}} \right) \right] + \mu_{voc} * V_{oc,ref} * \Delta T \quad (18)$$

where G_{ref} is the reference solar radiation: 1000 W/m² and G_β is the global horizontal radiation calculated using Equation (1). Knowing the current of the panel and its voltage, the output power (P_{pv}) is determined via Equation (19).

$$P_{pv} = V_{pv} * I_{pv} \quad (19)$$

The constants C_1 and C_2 in Equation (17) are given by Equations (20) and (21).

$$C_1 = \left(1 - \frac{I_{mp,ref}}{I_{sc,ref}} \right) \exp \left(\frac{-V_{mp,ref}}{C_2 V_{oc,ref}} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\frac{V_{mp,ref}}{V_{oc,ref}} - 1}{\ln \left(1 - \frac{I_{mp,ref}}{I_{sc,ref}} \right)} \quad (21)$$

Equation (22) gives the panel current variation (ΔI).

$$\Delta I = \mu_{I_{sc}} * I_{sc,ref} \left(\frac{G_{\beta}}{G_{ref}} \right) \Delta T + \left(\frac{G_{\beta}}{G_{ref}} - 1 \right) I_{sc,ref} \quad (22)$$

where ΔT corresponds to the temperature variation of the panel and is calculated using Equation (23).

$$\Delta T = T_e + G_{\beta} \left(\frac{NOCT - 20}{800} \right) - T_{cell,ref} \quad (23)$$

where T_e corresponds to the ambient temperature measured experimentally and obtained from the data in [13]. Reference values such as cell temperature, normal operating temperature, and open circuit voltage, among others, are necessary to operate the above power modeling equations and are extracted from technical datasheets. Table 1 presents these technical parameters for a 600 W solar panel.

Table 1. Technical parameters of the solar panel for modeling the power produced [17]

Technical Parameter	Symbol	Value
Cell Type	----	Monocrystalline
Nominal power [W]	P	600
Open Circuit Voltage [V]	$V_{oc,ref}$	41.6
Short-circuit current [A]	$I_{sc,ref}$	18.32
Voltage at Maximum Power [V]	$V_{mp,ref}$	34.7
Current at Maximum Power [A]	$I_{mp,ref}$	17.3
Nominal Cell Operating Temperature [°C]	$NOCT$	44
Temperature coefficient of V_{oc} [%/°C]	μ_{Voc}	-0.25
Temperature coefficient of I_{sc} [%/°C]	μ_{Isc}	0.04

The production of green hydrogen relies on the direct coupling of a photovoltaic system to a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer with a nominal power of 120 kW, whose technical data are presented in Table 2 and its polarization curve in Figure 1.

Table 2. Some Technical Parameters of the 120kW Electrolyzer

Technical Parameter	Value	Fountain
Number of cells	54	[18]
Nominal power [kW]	120	[19]
Maximum operating power [kW]	116.6	[19]
Minimum operating power [kW]	2.5	[19]
Exhaust pressure [bar]	30	[20]

Figure 1. Polarization curve of 120 kW PEM electrolyzer [19]

The polarization curve gives the operating current of the electrolyzer to estimate the molar flows of hydrogen and oxygen. The production equations were defined as explained by Ghribi [14] and Sartori et al. [21]. The molar fluxes of water (\dot{n}_{H_2O}), hydrogen (\dot{n}_{H_2}) and oxygen (\dot{n}_{O_2}) are given by Equation (24).

$$\dot{n} = \frac{I}{zF} \quad ; \quad \dot{n} = \frac{3.6I}{zF} \quad (24)$$

where z corresponds to the number of electrons: 2 for hydrogen and 4 for oxygen, and F is the Faraday constant. The molar flow of water is equivalent to the molar flow of hydrogen according to the chemical reaction ($H_2O \rightarrow H_2 + 1/2O_2$). The volumetric fluxes of hydrogen (\dot{V}_{H_2}) and oxygen (\dot{V}_{O_2}) are given by Equation (25).

$$\dot{V}_{gas} = \frac{\dot{n}_{gas}RT_a}{P} n_c \eta_f \quad (25)$$

where R is the ideal gas constant, n_c is the number of cells in the electrolyzer, P is the outlet pressure of the gases, and η_f is the Faraday efficiency. Equation (26) gives the volumetric flow of water consumption (\dot{V}_{H_2O}).

$$\dot{V}_{H_2O} = \frac{\dot{n}_{H_2O} M_{H_2O}}{\rho_{H_2O}} n_c \quad (26)$$

where M_{H_2O} is the molecular mass of water, and ρ_{H_2O} is the density of water at ambient temperature. Equation (27) gives mass fluxes of both hydrogen and oxygen.

$$\dot{m}_{gas} = \rho_{gas} * \dot{V}_{gas} \quad (27)$$

where ρ_{gas} is the gas density at ambient temperature and 30 bar. Finally, the water consumption rate (\dot{m}_{H_2O}) is calculated using Equation (28).

$$\dot{m}_{H_2O} = \dot{n}_{H_2O} * M_{H_2O} \quad (28)$$

The variables using these equations, such as ambient temperature, ideal gas properties, efficiency, and Faraday's constant, are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Constants and Variables Required for Electrolyzer Flow Modeling

Constants and Variables	Symbol	Value	Source
Electrolyzer Current [A]	I	Variable depending on the polarization curve	[19]
Number of electrons	z	2 for hydrogen, 4 for oxygen	[14], [21]
Faraday's constant [C/mol]	F	96,485	[14], [21]
Ambient temperature [°C] - [K]	T _a	25 - 298.15	[14]
The universal ideal gas constant [kJ/kmol. K]	R	8.314	[14]
Faraday Efficiency	η _f	0.99	[14]
Molar mass of water [kg/kmol]	M _{H₂O}	18.015	Common Domain
Water density at ambient temperature [kg/m ³]	ρ _{H₂O}	997.05	Common Domain
Hydrogen density at 30 bar and ambient temperature [kg/m ³]	ρ _{H₂}	2.44	Ideal Gas Equation of State

Oxygen density at 30 bar and ambient temperature [kg/m ³]	ρ_{O_2}	38.73	Ideal Gas Equation of State
---	--------------	-------	-----------------------------

2.2 Use of hydrogen in haulage mining trucks

The open-pit coal mine considered in this study has 121 are Komatsu® 930E-4. In the electric traction of this truck, the diesel engine is coupled to an AC generator to power two three-phase induction motors [22], [23]. Table 4 summarizes technical data.

Table 4. Technical Specifications of Komatsu 930E-4 Haulage Mining Truck [22], [23]

Truck	
	Komatsu® 930E-4
Load capacity [ton]	320
Traction	Electric
Engine	Cummins QSK60
No. of cylinders	16V
Nominal power [kW/hp]	2014 / 2700
Aspiration	Turbocharged (2 stages)
Maximum rotational speed [rpm]	1900
Weight [kg/lb]	9608 / 21182
Compression Ratio	14.5:1
Bore – stroke [mm]	159 – 190
Displacement [L]	60.2
Fuel consumption [g/kWh]	200 g/kWh @ 1500 rpm
Maximum torque [Nm]	9945 @ 1500 rpm

A conversion process from a typical diesel engine to a dual-fuel operation can be done with minimal modifications. For example, the conversion to dual CNG-diesel involves only the assembly of auxiliary instrumentation and retrofit kit without making any changes to the engine [24], [25]. Although these diesel engine to dual CNG-diesel operation conversion technologies exist, their commercial implementation in mining trucks has not advanced significantly. Some applications have been achieved in the Canadian mining sector, where natural gas operation has focused on dual diesel-LNG (liquefied natural gas) conversion with systems provided by GFS Corp., as shown in Figure 2 [26].

Figure 2. Implementation of LNG technology and conversion of a CAT 793B mining truck to dual-mode LNG-diesel [26]

On the other hand, in Australia, progress is being made in terms of mining transport trucks operating in dual mode with CNG. Companies in the sector are collaborating to develop high-density compressed natural gas (HDCNG), mainly focused on mining machines, the application of which has already taken place in the CAT 789C truck [26]. This conversion technology is versatile as it can be deployed in various mining vehicles. HDCNG fuel kits are installed on the truck using fuel cabinets. Each cabinet houses two lightweight composite cylinders designed to be robotically swapped during refueling, as shown in Figure 3 [26].

Figure 3. HDCNG Storage System For CAT 789C Mining Truck Dual Operation, Australia Case [26]

Dual diesel-hydrogen conversion of mining trucks faces many more restrictions than natural gas. The first problem when installing a diesel-hydrogen dual-mode conversion kit arises when identifying the available space on the truck for the gaseous fuel containers. Although hydrogen has a higher calorific value than CNG (120 MJ/kg for hydrogen and 45 MJ/kg for CNG), its low density requires high volumetric storage capacities. The reduction in diesel fuel consumption in the mining truck will depend on the number of hydrogen containers that can be placed in the truck, typically reaching a fuel-saving percentage of less than 20%, which corresponds to an even lower saving percentage than that achieved with CNG (60% on average).

Assuming that the structural design of the trucks is the same, changing only their dimensions and according to a rigorous evaluation of the space available in a similar truck, three main configurations could be established for the placement of the hydrogen accumulation system. Figure 4 shows the

position of a set of parallel containers (green) adjacent to the diesel fuel tank in one of the CAT® trucks. Figure 5 also shows the position of the same set of containers, but now perpendicularly. This configuration may not be appropriate since there may be risks associated with hydrogen safety on the mining truck.

Figure 4. Parallel dual-tank configuration for hydrogen storage next to the diesel fuel tank on the mining truck

Figure 5. Perpendicular dual-tank configuration for hydrogen storage next to the diesel fuel tank on the mining truck

Finally, Figure 6 shows a configuration of serial containers placed at the front of the mining truck, like the HDCNG container assembly presented in Figure 3. This configuration is perhaps the most

suitable for the location of the set of containers, taking advantage of the area with the most space in the mining truck.

Figure 6. Serial configuration of containers for hydrogen storage in the space next to the main cabin

The only viable location is the space adjacent to the driver cab, as the design and dimensions of the mining trucks described above do not allow for any other suitable space. Thus, it is possible to conclude that a series of a maximum of eight (8) containers can be placed on the truck, and the amount of hydrogen stored depends on the dimensions of the selected container at a tank pressure of 550 bar. For the diesel engine of the mining truck, a high-precision fuel injection system with special injectors that can handle diesel and hydrogen is needed. Considering that trucks undergo an average of two refuelings per day, it is also important to assume that the hydrogen will be refueled at the same time as the diesel so that this does not significantly hinder the operation of the mining machine.

The main properties of diesel and hydrogen that will later be important to find the percentage of energy substitution to determine the amount of hydrogen required in the mining truck correspond to the lower heating value and density. For diesel, the values of these properties are 850 kg/m³ and 43.1 MJ/kg. Likewise, they are 0.08 kg/m³ and 120 MJ/kg for hydrogen. On the other hand, for estimating diesel fuel consumption in a standard operating cycle of a mining truck, the mode of operation data is taken according to a vehicle dynamics evaluation of a CAT® 777D truck with 800 kW nominal power, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Modes of Operation for a Standard Cycle of a CAT® 777D Mining Truck

Mode of Operation	Average Percentage
Empty Moving Vehicle	29.5%
Loaded Moving Vehicle	32.6%
Empty stopped vehicle	16.1%
Loaded Stopped Vehicle	5.54%
Stopped vehicle loading	16.3%

From this information, the vehicle idle time reaches an approximate value of 38% on average, leaving only 62% of the time available for fuel substitution. As a result of this analysis, it was found that the fuel consumption of the truck during 8 hours of operation was 100 gallons. From this information, an average representative consumption factor (F_c) can be determined as shown below:

$$F_c = \frac{100 \text{ gal diesel}}{8 \text{ h}} = 12.5 \frac{\text{gal}}{\text{h}} \text{ diesel} \approx 13 \frac{\text{gal}}{\text{h}} \text{ diesel}$$

Considering a linear magnitude relationship between the power of the trucks, the estimated average consumption for the trucks of the Cerrejón mine is determined from Equation (29).

$$F_{c_i} = \frac{P_i * F_c}{P} \quad (29)$$

Where F_{c_i} is the consumption factor for a given truck, P_i is its corresponding power, and P is the power of the CAT® 777D truck (800 kW). Table 6 shows the results of these factors, establishing a confidence range composed of three values. This range is assumed as adjustment values to the consumption factor to minimize the variabilities of that value about its significance concerning actual consumption.

Table 6. Fuel Consumption Factors Calculated for Haulage Truck and Definition of Confidence Range

Mining Truck	Komatsu 930E-4
Engine power [kW]	2014
Average Consumption Factor [gal/h]	33
Assumed Consumption Confidence Range [gal/h]	30-35-40

Once the consumption factors have been determined, the amount of hydrogen for partial substitution is determined. First, Equation (30) determines the amount of energy consumed by a mining truck E_i during a defined period of operation:

$$E_i = F_{c_i} * LHV_{diesel} * t \quad (30)$$

where LHV_{diesel} is the lower heating value of diesel defined in Table 3, and t corresponds to the operating time between refueling (12 hours).

2.3 Calculation of LCOE, LCOH and COOBH

The levelized cost of energy ($LCOE$) is determined considering the capital value method represented in Equation (31) [27].

$$LCOE = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{M_t}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (31)$$

where I_0 corresponds to the initial investment cost (capital cost) in dollars (USD), A_t represents the annual operation and maintenance costs (USD), M_t is the total power generation over a year (kWh), n is the lifetime of the system (years), and i it's the discount rate. LCOE results can be expressed in units of USD/kWh or commonly also in USD/MWh. The initial investment cost is calculated by considering the commercial price of the photovoltaic module in the area plus an aggregate percentage margin for labor and structural factors, among others. The result obtained will be evaluated based on values determined in the literature to verify its validity. After calculating the LCOE, the calculation of the LCOH considers the associated costs of each subsystem inherent to production [28], [29]. The $LCOH$ is determined by Equation (32) as follows:

$$LCOH = \frac{NPC}{\sum_{i=1}^n H_{P_i}} * RF(j, t) \quad (32)$$

where the NPC corresponds to the net present cost in USD, H_p is the amount of hydrogen generated during a year (kg) and RF corresponds to the capital recovery factor that depends on the interest rate j and the system's lifetime. This recovery factor is determined as set out in Equation (33):

$$RF(j, t) = \frac{j(1+j)^t}{(1+j)^t - 1} \quad (33)$$

On the other hand, the net present cost is determined from Equation (34) as follows:

$$NPC = C_T + C_{O\&M} + C_{REP} \quad (34)$$

where C_T is the cost of installing the system (initial investment cost), $C_{O\&M}$ is the cost of operation and maintenance, and C_{REP} is the cost of restitution of elements; all these costs are in USD. Equation (35) gives the installation costs.

$$C_T = \sum_{i=1}^n (C_x)_i \quad (35)$$

where C_x corresponds to the cost of each subsystem (photovoltaic plant, electrolyzer, low-pressure storage). Equation (36) gives the $C_{O\&M}$ costs.

$$C_{O\&M} = \gamma \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (C_y)_i \quad (36)$$

where γ is the annualization factor, C_y corresponds to the O&M cost for each production subsystem (solar plant, electrolyzer, low-pressure accumulation). The γ factor is determined via Equation (37).

$$\gamma = \frac{(1+j)^t - 1}{j(1+j)^t} \quad (37)$$

where j is the interest rate and t is the project lifetime. The total replacement cost of the C_{REP} elements is determined by Equation (38) as follows:

$$C_{REP} = \sum_{i=1}^n (C_z)_i * \mu_i \quad (38)$$

Where C_z corresponds to the replacement cost of elements whose life cycle is less than the project cycle (batteries, DC/DC controller). The μ factor shifts the future value of restitution costs and is determined using Equation (39).

$$\mu = \sum_{i=1}^{\left(\frac{t}{t_z}-1\right)} \left[1 + \frac{1}{(1+j)^{i \cdot t_z}} \right] \quad (39)$$

Where t_z is the life cycle time of each returnable element (10 years). For the calculation of the cost of hydrogen over the mining truck (COOBH), the previously determined LCOH will be considered to determine the initial capital cost of the required system. On the other hand, the costs of installation, O&M, and restitution of elements include:

- The hydrogen compressor system.
- Pre-accumulation cooling system in onboard containers.
- Additional photovoltaic plant for power supply for compressors and chiller.
- Battery bank for compressor and cooling system.
- Accumulation at 700 bar.
- Accumulation in onboard containers (550 bar)
- Hydrogen dispensing
- Hydrogen use system for dual engine operation.

Finally, Table 7 represents the cost structure and other economic data required to calculate the levelized costs of energy, hydrogen, and hydrogen onboard the mining truck.

Table 7. Economic data required for the calculation of levelized costs

Individual Costs	Unit	Value	Source
Cost of 600W PV Module	USD	323.47	[30]
Cost associated with structure, labor, wiring.	%	30	[31]

Operation and maintenance (O&M) cost of photovoltaic generator	%/year	1.58	[32]
DC/DC Power Converter Cost	USD	19752	[33]
Electrolyzer Installation Cost	USD/kW	335	[34]
Installation Cost: Low-Pressure Hydrogen Storage	USD/kgH ₂	298	[35]
Electrolyzer O&M cost (relative to installation cost)	%/year	2	[32]
O&M cost of low-pressure hydrogen storage (relative to installation cost)	%/year	1	[35]
Availability of water for electrolysis	USD/m ³	0.99	[36]
Cost of Restitution of Elements, Electrolyzer	%	30	[36]
Installation cost: hydrogen storage at 700 bar	USD/kgH ₂	906	[35]
Installation cost: hydrogen storage at 550 bar	USD/kgH ₂	850	[37]
Battery Bank Installation Cost	USD/unit	1477	[37]
Cost of installing hydrogen supply system to the engine	USD/kgH ₂	267	[38]
Inverter Installation Cost	USD/kW	70	[39]
Hydrogen Compressor System Cost	USD/kW	8635	[28]
Hydrogen Cooling System Installation Cost	USD/kW	5750	[32]
Hydrogen Compression O&M Cost	%/year	7	[35]
O&M Cost of Hydrogen Storage at 700 Bar	%/year	1	[40]
Cost of O&M battery bank (relative to installation cost)	%/year	3	[28]
Cost of O&M hydrogen delivery system in the truck	%/year	3	[38]
O&M Cost of Hydrogen Refrigeration System	%/year	3	[32]

Cost of replacement of elements, battery bank	%	30	[36]
Cost of restitution of elements, inverter	%	30	[36]
Project lifetime	years	25	[41]
Restitution time of elements (batteries, inverters)	years	10	[32]
Cost associated with structure, labor, wiring.	%	30	[31]
Discount rate (case of Colombia)	%	12	[42]

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Solar radiation and PV energy

The components of solar radiation per hour were determined, and the global radiation was determined from the sum of these components. Figure 7 shows the behavior of this radiation on an inclined surface throughout the year [43], [44].

Figure 7. Hourly global solar radiation on an inclined surface throughout the year

For each day, the peak of solar radiation occurs at around 12 h, given the sun's position in the sky, and it has an average value of 800 to 900 W/m^2 . Concerning the energy produced by a photovoltaic module, the voltage and current values produced by the panel were determined. Figure 8 shows this power for a 600 W panel whose highest values are in the midday hours with values between 420 W and 480 W.

Figure 8. Output power produced by a 600 W photovoltaic panel throughout the year

Knowing the peak power value reached by the photovoltaic panel of approximately 471.7 W and knowing that the maximum operating power of the electrolyzer cannot be exceeded, the size of the renewable plant for its energy supply is determined. The size of the photovoltaic generator corresponds to 247 panels, and in Figure 9, the efficiency analysis for the energy production of the photovoltaic generator is shown. For February and November, the behavior of the efficiency of the panel begins to grow from the morning hours until it reaches a constant value of approximately 18%. For the other months, the behavior of efficiency is similar because the curves are located between and around the two curves shown. This value is a reasonable result for high-quality solar panels and is close to the 21.2% operating efficiency listed in the specification sheet [17].

Figure 9. Determination of the energy production efficiency of the photovoltaic generator

3.2 Electrolyzer gas production and water consumption

The amounts of hydrogen produced by the electrolyzer are obtained, which allows the total annual production to be established throughout the year. These results are shown in Figure 10, where hydrogen production ranges from 13.6 to 16.5 kg/d.

Figure 10. Hydrogen production over the year

In this way, the total production of approximately 5492.84 kilograms of hydrogen per year for an electrolyzer is obtained with a water consumption of 49.74 m³. Figure 11 presents the analysis of the efficiency of the PEM electrolyzer for each month of the year, considering the energy supply from the photovoltaic generator and hydrogen energy production. In February and November, the efficiency of the electrolyzer has values above 50%, given that from the early hours of operation, it starts with an efficiency of approximately 80% until stabilizing at approximately 70%, coinciding with literature values for PEM electrolyzer, which lie between 60% and 80% [45], [46]. It should be noted that as in Figure 9, in the other months the efficiency behavior is similar because the curves are located between and around the two curves shown.

Figure 11. Determination of electrolyzer production efficiency

3.3 Sizing of the hydrogen production plant for mining trucks

Below is the dimensioning of the renewable hydrogen production and supply system for a mining truck at the open-pit coal mine, corresponding to the and Komatsu® 930E-4. Table 8 presents the input requirements for determining the installed capacities of the subsystems. Based on this information, the annual production and other aspects related to installed capacities are determined.

Table 8. Input requirements for the sizing of the renewable hydrogen production and supply system for the mining truck

Input requirement	Value
Truck	Komatsu® 930E-4
No. of containers on the truck	8
Container capacity [kg]	4
Hydrogen refueling per day	2
Diesel Fuel Consumption Factor [gal/h]	30-35-40

Thus, Table 9 shows the installed capacities of the subsystems that comprise the renewable hydrogen production and supply system, in addition to the annual hydrogen production required. The size of the plant is proportional to the increase in the energy requirement of the truck, considering that a greater amount of hydrogen would need to be produced to meet the demand of this increase in size. It should be noted that the determined system is on a small scale, considering the selection of one mining truck. Based on this, the sizing of the associated systems was carried out for the required hydrogen demand.

Table 9. Hydrogen Production and Installed Production and Supply System Capacities for Mining Truck

Mining Truck	Komatsu® 930E-4
Annual hydrogen requirement [kg]	27,431.5
Daily accumulation capacity [kg]	64
Installed PV Capacity [MW]	0.63
Installed Capacity of Electrolyzer [MW]	0.58
Installed Capacity Compressor System [kW]	26.6
Installed Battery Bank Capacity [MWh]	0.98

Installed Capacity H₂-precooling [kW]	35.82
---	-------

Finally, by calculating the percentage of energy that would replace hydrogen on the mining truck, it was possible to establish, as presented in Figure 12, it is observed that about the Komatsu® 930E-4 truck, several percentages of energy substitution can be achieved with values between 5.8% and 7.7% for different fuel consumption rates (30, 35, and 40 gal/h).

Figure 12. Percentage of partial energy substitution of diesel by hydrogen respect to the fuel consumption of Komatsu® 930E-4 mining truck

3.4 LCOE, LCOH and COOBH

Below is the result of the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) calculated for the photovoltaic generation plant of the renewable hydrogen production system. The economic data in Table 7 are the main requirements in conjunction with the capacity size of the subsystems for calculating total related costs. Thus, Table 10 presents these results, where an initial investment of more than 720 thousand dollars is needed for the photovoltaic generation plant.

Table 10. Determination of the initial investment cost for the photovoltaic generator of the renewable hydrogen production system

Component	Quantity	Unit Cost [USD/un]	Total [USD]
600 W photovoltaic panels	1367	323.47	442,183.49
DC/DC Current Converter	6	19,752.09	118,512.54
Costs associated with structure, labor, and wiring.	-----	30%	168,208.81
Total Cost of Capital Investing			728,904.84

With the factors corresponding to the discount rate, the initial capital value determined, the percentage of O&M, and the total energy produced by the photovoltaic field in the year, the LCOE is determined. Table 11 shows the calculation of this value, which is equal to 0.0666 USD/kWh or 66.63 USD/MWh, which allows us to define that this photovoltaic generator can produce 1 MWh for 66.63 USD.

Table 11. Calculating the Levelized Cost of LCOE Energy from a Photovoltaic Generator

Related Factor	Value
Cost of Capital [USD]	728,904.84
O&M Cost [USD]	11,516.70
Annual energy production [kWh]	1,567,667.37
Levelized Cost of Energy LCOE [USD/kWh]	0.06663
Levelized Cost of Energy LCOE [USD/MWh]	66.63

On the other hand, a comparison was made between this calculated LCOE and equivalent values calculated in Colombia. In the literature, levelized cost of energy values of 0.054 USD/kWh, 0.054 USD/kWh, and 0.0716 USD/kWh corresponding to the research of Burdack et al. [27], Saldarriaga et al. [47], and López et al. [48], allow establishing that about the LCOE determined in this study has an adequate approximation. The LCOE thus becomes input information for the calculation of the renewable LCOH. Variables related to the electrolyzer, low-pressure accumulation, water consumption, and other associated variables are related. The project analysis is established for a lifetime of 25 years, so it was also necessary to include the costs of restitution of elements. With this, the total costs for determining the LCOH are calculated. Thus, Table 12 shows the synthesis of these costs.

Table 12. Determination of initial costs, O&M, and restitution of elements for the renewable hydrogen production plant

Component	Quantity	Unit Cost [USD/un]	Total [USD]
PEM Electrolyzation Plant Capacity [kW]	580	335.16 USD/kW	194,392.80
Energy delivered by PV generator [kWh]	1,567,667.37	0.06663 USD/kWh	104,453.68
Low-pressure hydrogen storage facility [kgH ₂]	75.2	298.52 USD/kgH ₂	22,448.70
Battery Bank Installation [Unit]	40	1477.52 USD	59,100.80
The cost associated with structure, labor, and wiring.	-----	30%	114,118.79

Annual water consumption [m ³]	294.41	0.99 USD/m ³	291.47
Electrolyzer O&M	-----	2%	3,887.86
O&M Low-Pressure Hydrogen Storage	-----	1%	224.49
O&M Battery Bank	-----	3%	1,773.02
Restitution of elements, electrolyzer	-----	30%	58,317.84
Replacement of elements, battery bank	-----	30%	17,730.24

Table 13 presents the calculation of LCOH, where this value turned out to be 6.2 USD/kgH₂, which indicates that the production of 1 kilogram of renewable hydrogen in the mine costs on average 6.2 USD over the plant lifetime.

Table 13. LCOH calculation for the hydrogen production system

Related Factor	Value
Cost of Capital [USD]	390,061.10
O&M Cost [USD]	867,690.27
Restitution Cost [USD]	76,048.08
Annual hydrogen production [kgH ₂]	27,431.5
Recovery Factor	0.1275
LCOH Hydrogen Levelized Cost [USD/kgH₂]	6.20

This LCOH is compared with different values established in the literature to verify how valid this result may be. From this comparison with research in the Colombian territory of Burdack et al. [18], Cobo et al. [21], and in the hydrogen roadmap [22], it can be highlighted that there is a similarity of the value calculated in this research with the others given that their values are respectively 5.88 USD/kgH₂, 5.01 USD/kgH₂ and 4.8 USD/kgH₂. Finally, another important indicator is the electrolyzer's full load hours (FLH) of operation to support the calculation of the LCOH. The FLH throughout the year are maintained in the range of 9 to 11 h per day, and the total FLH during the year amounts to 3740, which allows us to establish that with a factor of 0.9 due to unforeseen events or plant shutdowns, the total effective FLH is equal to 3366 hours. According to Smolinka & Garche [23], an electrolyzer's average operation varies between 3300 and 4400 hours; therefore, the FLH determined here is very favorable.

The LCOH thus becomes input information for calculating the cost of hydrogen over the mining truck (COOBH). In the analysis of the project, it is also established for the lifetime, so it was also necessary to include the costs of restitution of elements in addition to initial capital costs and O&M. With this information, the total costs for the determination of the COOBH are calculated as shown in Table 14.

Table 14. Determination of initial costs, O&M, and restitution of elements associated with the hydrogen onboard the mining truck

Component	Quantity	Unit Cost [USD/un]	Total [USD]
Hydrogen supplied [kgH ₂]	27,431.5	6.20 USD/kgH ₂	170,075.3
Energy delivered by PV generator [kWh]	150,230	0.06663 USD/kWh	10,009.82
Hydrogen storage at 700 bar [kgH ₂]	75.2	906.22 USD/kgH ₂	68,147.74
Hydrogen storage at 550 bar [kgH ₂]	75.2	850 USD/kgH ₂	63,920
Battery Bank Installation [Unit]	8	1477.52 USD	11,820.16
Hydrogen supply system to the engine [kgH ₂]	75.2	266.67 USD/kgH ₂	20,053.58
Inverters [kW]	63	70 USD/kW	4,410
Hydrogen compressor system [kW]	26.6	8,634.84 USD/kW	229,686.74
Hydrogen Cooling System [kW]	35.8	5,750.18 USD/kW	205,856.44
The cost associated with structure, labor, and wiring.	-----	30%	181,168.40
O&M Hydrogen Compression	-----	7%	16,078.07
O&M hydrogen storage at 700 bar	-----	1%	681.48
O&M hydrogen storage at 550 bar	-----	1%	639.20
O&M Battery Bank	-----	3%	354.60
O&M hydrogen supply system in the truck	-----	3%	601.61
O&M Hydrogen Cooling System	-----	3%	6,175.69

Restitution of elements, inverters	-----	30%	1,323
Replacement of elements, battery bank	-----	30%	3,546.05

Table 15 presents the COOBH calculation, where this value turned out to be 10.29 USD/kgH₂, which indicates that placing 1 kilogram of renewable hydrogen in the mining truck for dual operation costs an average of 10.29 USD over the entire useful life of the plant.

Table 15. Calculating the cost of onboard hydrogen (COOBH)

Related Factor	Value
Cost of Capital [USD]	603,894.68
O&M Cost [USD]	1,604,829.65
Restitution Cost [USD]	4,869.05
Annual hydrogen production [kgH ₂]	23,431.5
Recovery Factor	0.1275
Cost of onboard hydrogen COOBH [USD/kgH₂]	10.29

3.5 Comparison of COOBH with international diesel price scenarios

The assessment of the economic scenarios encompassed by the international price is required to understand the competitiveness of hydrogen as a fuel source. Table 16 presents a first comparative approach between the LCOH and COOBH concerning the international diesel price on the Gulf Coast, where the fuel for the mining machinery operation in the mine is purchased.

Table 16. Initial comparison of the LCOH and COOBH with the international price of diesel in the Gulf Coast

LCOH	6.20 USD/kgH ₂	51.67 USD/GJ	This research
COOBH	10.29 USD/kgH ₂	85.75 USD/GJ	This research
Diesel Price (Gulf Coast)	4.17 USD/gal	30.07 USD/GJ	[49]

As seen in the table above, comparing a hydrogen energy cost of 51.67 USD/GJ and 85.75 USD/GJ with the diesel price of 30.07 USD/GJ suggests a significant difference in economic viability in the current context. In this case, hydrogen is more expensive than diesel. However, it is important to consider factors such as the fluctuation of the price of diesel in the market, which in the future may be an opportunity to consider possible increases, arousing even more interest in renewable hydrogen as an element of additional value for companies and industries seeking to meet environmental

objectives and stricter regulations. In addition, the assessment of projected hypothetical scenarios of the international diesel price becomes a key tool for the economic viability of the COOBH. Decision-making should be based on a comprehensive analysis considering immediate costs, long-term benefits, and market trends. That is why, given the complexity of the economic assessment between renewable hydrogen and diesel, an approximation is proposed by defining three scenarios of the international diesel price. These scenarios would include a high diesel price scenario, a low diesel price scenario, and a baseline scenario based on current market prices. However, as there are no detailed reports in the literature on the projections of the international diesel price in the Gulf Coast, the assessment will be based on the variability of oil production since this is the main factor affecting the price of liquid fuels. It is worth mentioning that these scenarios are assumed by the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) to analyze the different environments of variability that could affect energy trends [50]. The scenarios are as follows:

- **Baseline scenario:** this is the main basis of the price defined by the laws and regulations in force until mid-November 2023, without considering possible future laws or regulations. In addition, it assumes that the price of Brent crude oil will reach 101 USD/barrel by the year 2050 [50].
- **High oil price scenario:** implies that the price of Brent oil will reach 190 USD/barrel by the year 2050 [50].
- **Low oil price scenario:** states that the price of Brent oil will reach 51 USD/barrel by the year 2050 [50].

To achieve an objective estimate focused on diesel, it is crucial to determine a correlation factor between the price of Brent oil (80.85 USD/barrel to date [49]) and the price of diesel so that with the prices mentioned in each scenario, the estimated price of diesel is determined using the correlation factor. To calculate this factor, the price of oil in USD/gal is first obtained, and then the quotient of the price of diesel divided by the price of oil is determined, which results in 2.166. Now, with this factor, diesel prices were determined according to each scenario as follows:

- **Baseline scenario:** diesel price will reach 5.21 USD/gal (37.57 USD/GJ) by 2050.
- **High diesel price scenario:** diesel price will reach 9.8 USD/gal (70.67 USD/GJ) by 2050.
- **Low diesel price scenario:** diesel price will decrease to 2.63 USD/gal (18.97 USD/GJ) by 2050.

Thus, conducting the COOBH analysis of the proposed scenarios, its value of 85.75 USD/GJ indicates a relatively high cost for the use of hydrogen compared to the projected diesel prices in the three scenarios. The high diesel price scenario is still lower than the COOBH, and although there is a narrower gap from the baseline scenario, hydrogen is still the most expensive option. There is a strong probability that the diesel price trend will tilt towards an increase. At the same time, research shows that the cost of LCOH hydrogen will see a decline by 2050, driven by technological advances, economies of scale, and improvements in production efficiency [18], [21], [22]. This potential scenario could improve the competitiveness of hydrogen and its economic viability as a renewable source. Table 17 shows the projection of the LCOH and COOBH for the economic scenarios of 2030 and 2050. It is worth mentioning that the COOBH estimate was made according to a correlation factor of 1.658 calculated based on the LCOH and COOBH values of this study.

Table 17. Economic projection of the LCOH and COOBH towards the 2030 and 2050 scenarios

Cost	2030 Scenario	2050 Scenario	Source
LCOH	2.7 USD/kgH ₂ 22.5 USD/GJ	1.7 USD/kgH ₂ 14.17 USD/GJ	[51], [52]
COOBH	4.48 USD/kgH ₂ 37.31 USD/GJ	2.82 USD/kgH ₂ 23.48 USD/GJ	Factor-Calculated

According to these results, it would be expected that in the future, producing hydrogen for use in the mining truck at a competitive cost would be viable considering both the reference scenarios, such as the high price of diesel for the years 2030 and 2050, according to its value of 37.31 USD/GJ and 23.48 USD/GJ, which is relatively lower than the scenarios mentioned above. This is because the country expects growth in the use of hydrogen in the mining sector by 2036, contributing approximately between 11% and 16% energetically in operations thanks to application policies in machinery [51].

3.6 CO₂ emissions

This analysis is carried out about the CO₂ emissions that could be saved by implementing renewable hydrogen as a fuel in mining trucks, establishing a direct relationship with diesel savings. First, a value of 7.7% was the maximum percentage of energy substitution of hydrogen estimated for the Komatsu® 930E-4 truck with an average diesel consumption of 30 gal/h. On the other hand, the analysis is made on a standard operating time of 12 hours, equivalent to the time between refueling. Similarly, a CO₂ emission factor of 3.186 kg-CO₂/kg-diesel is defined for a mining truck, considering that this value is essential to evaluate the environmental impact of the analyzed vehicle [26]. Based on this information and after the calculations have been developed, the results can be seen in Table 18, where the savings in CO₂ emissions during the operating time of the mining truck, whose value reached 284.13 kg-CO₂, were estimated.

Table 18. Estimating Emission Savings During the Operating Time of the Komatsu® 930E-4 Mining Truck

Fuel consumption rate (100% diesel) [kg-diesel/h]	96.52
Fuel consumption rate (92.3% diesel) [kg-diesel/h]	89.09
Difference [kg-diesel/h]	7.43
CO₂ emissions saved during operation time (12 hours) [kg-CO₂]	284.13

Thanks to this saving value, it was possible to define a new emission saving factor equivalent to 23.68 kg-CO₂/h, which suggests that with 7.7% diesel energy substitution for renewable hydrogen, 23.68

kilograms of CO₂ are not emitted for each hour of truck operation. On the other hand, to assess the environmental viability of the use of hydrogen, a CO₂ tax was determined about the savings in emissions thanks to the partial fuel substitution. These results are shown in Table 19.

Table 19. Calculation of the CO₂ emissions tax to ensure the viability of the COOBH in the mining truck

Diesel Saved	89.18 kg – 27.72 gal	115.59 USD
Hydrogen consumed	32 kg	329.28 USD
Difference		213.69 USD
Calculated CO₂ tax		0.75207 USD/kg-CO ₂ 752.07 USD/ton-CO ₂

As can be seen, the calculated tax resulted in a value of 752.07 USD/ton-CO₂, which is significantly high compared to current carbon tax standards in most countries. Therefore, for industries, this outcome could significantly impact industries and companies, especially those that rely heavily on fossil fuels, as it can raise concerns about the competitiveness and economic stability of their operations. Table 20 shows the value of the CO₂ tax adopted by some countries in America [27].

Table 20. Tax on CO₂ emissions from countries in the Americas [53]

Country	CO₂ tax [USD/ton-CO₂]
Colombia	5.06
Argentina	3.27
Chile	5.00
Uruguay	155.87
Mexico	4.07
Canada	48.03

Based on the information in the table above, it is possible to determine that the calculated tax significantly differs from the carbon taxes of these countries. This allows us to conclude that renewable hydrogen would be environmentally viable, but not economically given that there is no balance between COOBH and CO₂ emission savings.

Figure 13. Variation of the tax on CO₂ emissions about the COOBH and comparison with the tax of the countries in the American continent

However, in Figure 13, which shows the variation of the CO₂ tax calculated in this study from the COOBH and compared with the taxes, it is possible to determine the equilibrium point that the COOBH must have for renewable hydrogen to be environmentally viable. Thus, in the case of Paraguay, the COOBH must have a value below 5.15 USD/kgH₂; for Canada, it must have a value below 4.09 USD/kgH₂; and for Colombia, Chile, Mexico, and Argentina, it must have a value below 3.65 USD/kgH₂. This would imply that the LCOH decreases its value to 3.14 USD/kgH₂, 2.49 USD/kgH₂, and 2.22 USD/kgH₂, respectively.

4. Conclusions

This study evaluated technically and economically the partial substitution of diesel by renewable hydrogen in a haulage mining truck. Through the analysis of hydrogen production costs, the viability of this fuel as an alternative to diesel in the mining sector has been evaluated. The results obtained provide a detailed view of the technical and economic aspects associated with the transition to hydrogen, considering key variables such as the levelized cost of energy (LCOE), the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH), and the cost of hydrogen on the mining truck (COOBH).

The modeling of the solar radiation and power produced by the photovoltaic generator was achieved, thus allowing a detailed analysis of hydrogen production to be carried out. This analysis was based on the specific energy demand of the electrolyzer, incorporating key factors such as the efficiency of the photovoltaic generator, which corresponded to 18%, and the electrolyzer, which corresponded to 70%. The installed capacity of the hydrogen production and supply system, calculated at 0.58 MW,

ensures an annual production of more than 27,000 kgH₂. In addition, when analyzing the substitution percentages, it is observed that the Komatsu® 930E-4 truck shows favorable values between 5.8% and 7.7% in terms of partial energy substitution compared to its diesel consumption.

An LCOE obtained of 66.63 USD/MWh and an LCOH obtained of 6.2 USD/kgH₂ in the mine are competitive, according to data from the literature. However, it is impossible to establish that the COOBH is not competitive considering its 10.29 USD/kgH₂ value, which is significantly higher than the international diesel price. A tax of 752.07 USD/t-CO₂ was found to be excessively high concerning the margin of carbon taxes defined for American countries. What can provide the possibility of making COOBH environmentally viable is the minimization of LCOH to 3.14 USD/kgH₂, 2.49 USD/kgH₂, and 2.22 USD/kgH₂, a fact that can be achieved in future scenarios for 2030 and 2050.

In future scenarios, technological advances and improvements in production processes are expected to allow hydrogen to be generated at more affordable costs. With these developments, hydrogen is anticipated to compete sustainably and economically viable with liquid fossil fuels, paving the way for a more effective transition to cleaner and more sustainable energy sources in the mining industry and, ultimately, the national energy matrix.

Acknowledgments

MINCIENCIAS supported this work through the National 810th Master's Scholarship Regiones 2018 Contract UN-OJ-2023-57665. DCS would like to acknowledge the support granted by the Department of Mechanical Engineering of Universidad del Norte from Barranquilla, Colombia.

References

- [1] R. L. Figueiredo, J. M. da Silva, and C. E. A. Ortiz, "Green hydrogen: Decarbonization in mining - Review," *Cleaner Energy Systems*, vol. 5. Elsevier B.V., Aug. 01, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.cles.2023.100075.
- [2] H. Bao, P. Knights, M. Kizil, and M. Nehring, "Electrification Alternatives for Open Pit Mine Haulage," *Mining*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–25, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/mining3010001.
- [3] Y. Feng and Z. Dong, "Optimal energy management strategy of fuel-cell battery hybrid electric mining truck to achieve minimum lifecycle operation costs," *Int J Energy Res*, vol. 44, no. 13, pp. 10797–10808, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1002/er.5728.
- [4] J. Yin, J. Wang, J. You, H. Chen, and W. Shi, "Integrated Energy System Optimal Operation in Coal District With Hydrogen Heavy Trucks," *Front Energy Res*, vol. 9, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2021.748673.
- [5] R. K. Ahluwalia, X. Wang, D. D. Papadias, and A. G. Star, "Performance and Total Cost of Ownership of a Fuel Cell Hybrid Mining Truck," *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 16, no. 1, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/en16010286.
- [6] C. Fúnez Guerra *et al.*, "Viability analysis of underground mining machinery using green hydrogen as a fuel," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 5112–5121, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.07.250.
- [7] L. Al-Ghussain, A. D. Ahmad, A. M. Abubaker, K. Hovi, M. A. Hassan, and A. Annuk, "Techno-economic feasibility of hybrid PV/wind/battery/thermal storage trigeneration system: Toward 100% energy independency and green hydrogen production," *Energy Reports*, vol. 9, pp. 752–772, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.egyr.2022.12.034.

- [8] B. Lumbers, J. Barley, and F. Platte, "Low-emission hydrogen production via the thermo-catalytic decomposition of methane for the decarbonisation of iron ore mines in Western Australia," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 47, no. 37, pp. 16347–16361, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.03.124.
- [9] S. H. Hosseini *et al.*, "Use of hydrogen in dual-fuel diesel engines," *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, vol. 98. Elsevier Ltd, Sep. 01, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.pecs.2023.101100.
- [10] M. Deb, G. R. K. Sastry, P. K. Bose, and R. Banerjee, "An experimental study on combustion, performance and emission analysis of a single cylinder, 4-stroke DI-diesel engine using hydrogen in dual fuel mode of operation," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 40, no. 27, pp. 8586–8598, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.04.125.
- [11] P. Dimitriou, M. Kumar, T. Tsujimura, and Y. Suzuki, "Combustion and emission characteristics of a hydrogen-diesel dual-fuel engine," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 43, no. 29, pp. 13605–13617, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.05.062.
- [12] European Commission (a), "Daily irradiance data PVGIS-5 geo-temporal irradiation database Provided inputs Outline of horizon at chosen location.," Feb. 2023. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/legal-notice_en
- [13] European Commission (b), "Daily temperature data PVGIS-5 geo-temporal irradiation database Provided inputs Outline of horizon at chosen location.," Feb. 2023. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/legal-notice_en
- [14] D. Ghribi, A. Khelifa, S. Diaf, and M. Belhamel, "Study of hydrogen production system by using PV solar energy and PEM electrolyser in Algeria," in *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Jul. 2013, pp. 8480–8490. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2012.09.175.
- [15] A. Madhlopa, "Solar receivers for thermal power generation.," London, 2022.
- [16] A. Luque and S. Hegedus, *Handbook of photovoltaic science and engineering*. Wiley, 2011.
- [17] Risen Energy, "Titan high performance monocrystalline PERC module," Sep. 2021.
- [18] R. Keller, E. Rauls, M. Hehemann, M. Müller, and M. Carmo, "An adaptive model-based feedforward temperature control of a 100 kW PEM electrolyzer," *Control Eng Pract*, vol. 120, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.conengprac.2021.104992.
- [19] K. Harrison, "2nd International Workshop Durability and Degradation Issues in PEM Electrolysis Cells and its Components Life-Time Prediction of PEM Water Electrolysis Stacks Coupled With RES Transportation," 2016.
- [20] J. Koponen, A. Kosonen, V. Ruuskanen, K. Huoman, M. Niemelä, and J. Ahola, "Control and energy efficiency of PEM water electrolyzers in renewable energy systems," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 50, pp. 29648–29660, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.10.056.
- [21] M. Sartory *et al.*, "Theoretical and experimental analysis of an asymmetric high pressure PEM water electrolyser up to 155 bar," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 52, pp. 30493–30508, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.10.112.
- [22] Komatsu America Corp., "Technical data of Komatsu 930E-4 electric drive mining truck," 2007.
- [23] Komatsu America Corp., "Technical data of Komatsu 960E-1 electric drive mining truck," 2008.

- [24] A. Tiwari, "Converting a Diesel Engine to Dual-Fuel Engine Using Natural Gas," *International Journal of Energy Science and Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 163–169, 2015, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29781.93926.
- [25] K. Bhavani and S. Murugesan, "Diesel to dual fuel conversion process development," *International Journal of Engineering and Technology(UAE)*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 306–310, 2018, doi: 10.14419/ijet.v7i3.6.15121.
- [26] InterGroup Consultants, "Natural gas as a fuel for mine haul trucks NRcan contract #: 3000631963 Final report," 2017.
- [27] A. Burdack, L. Duarte-Herrera, G. López-Jiménez, T. Polklas, and O. Vasco-Echeverri, "Techno-economic calculation of green hydrogen production and export from Colombia," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1685–1700, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.10.064.
- [28] S. Amara, S. Toumi, C. Ben Salah, and A. S. Saidi, "Improvement of techno-economic optimal sizing of a hybrid off-grid micro-grid system," *Energy*, vol. 233, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2021.121166.
- [29] Q. Hassan, I. S. Abdulrahman, H. M. Salman, O. T. Olapade, and M. Jaszczur, "Techno-Economic Assessment of Green Hydrogen Production by an Off-Grid Photovoltaic Energy System," *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 16, no. 2, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/en16020744.
- [30] Solarshop, "Solar panel 600 W monocristaline." Accessed: Nov. 23, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.solarshop.com.co/item-panel-solar-600w-monocristalino-22cd4139-62e1-36b0-4aed-f429e663a13a>
- [31] A. Komilov, "Location and orientation based LCOE: Simplified visual analysis and generalization of the levelized cost of electricity from storageless photovoltaic systems," *Int J Energy Res*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 5649–5658, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1002/er.6190.
- [32] M. Minutillo, A. Perna, A. Forcina, S. Di Micco, and E. Jannelli, "Analyzing the levelized cost of hydrogen in refueling stations with on-site hydrogen production via water electrolysis in the Italian scenario," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 26, pp. 13667–13677, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.11.110.
- [33] Tech Energo, "Controller DC/DC Siemens SINAMIC DCP 120 kW." Accessed: Nov. 23, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techenergo.net/6rp0010-1aa32-0aa0-zg33m79s03.html>
- [34] L. Povacz and R. Bhandari, "Analysis of the Levelized Cost of Renewable Hydrogen in Austria," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 15, no. 5, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15054575.
- [35] C. F. Guerra, L. Reyes-Bozo, E. Vyhmeister, J. L. Salazar, M. J. Caparrós, and C. Clemente-Jul, "Sustainability of hydrogen refuelling stations for trains using electrolyzers," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 26, pp. 13748–13759, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.10.044.
- [36] B. Olateju, A. Kumar, and M. Secanell, "A techno-economic assessment of large scale wind-hydrogen production with energy storage in Western Canada," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 41, no. 21, pp. 8755–8776, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.03.177.
- [37] Aliexpress, "GTK-Battery LiFepo4 96V - 250Ah." Accessed: Nov. 23, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://es.aliexpress.com/i/1005005707001781.html>

- [38] R. K. Ahluwalia, J.-K. Peng, H.-S. Roh, D. Papadimas, X. Wang, and S. M. Aceves, "Liquid hydrogen storage system for heavy duty trucks: Capacity, dormancy, refueling, and discharge," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.05.113.
- [39] V. Ramasamy, D. Feldman, J. Desai, and R. Margolis, "U.S. Solar Photovoltaic System and Energy Storage Cost Benchmarks: Q1 2021," 2021. [Online]. Available: www.nrel.gov/publications.
- [40] C. F. Guerra, L. Reyes-Bozo, E. Vyhmeister, J. L. Salazar, M. J. Caparrós, and C. Clemente-Jul, "Sustainability of hydrogen refuelling stations for trains using electrolyzers," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 26, pp. 13748–13759, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.10.044.
- [41] S. Dokhani, M. Assadi, and B. G. Pollet, "Techno-economic assessment of hydrogen production from seawater," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, no. 26, pp. 9592–9608, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.11.200.
- [42] DNP, *Tasa social de descuento Colombia*. 2022. Accessed: Nov. 23, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://colaboracion.dnp.gov.co/CDT/Normatividad/Justificacion%20tecnica%20-%20Tasa%20social%20de%20descuento.pdf>
- [43] M. J. Ahmad and G. N. Tiwari, "Study of Models for Predicting the Mean Hourly Global Radiation from Daily Summations," 2008.
- [44] M. Kleniewska, D. Mitrowska, and M. Wasilewicz, "Estimating daily global solar radiation with no meteorological data in poland," *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 10, no. 3, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.3390/app10030778.
- [45] J. Nieminen, I. Dincer, and G. Naterer, "Comparative performance analysis of PEM and solid oxide steam electrolyzers," *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 35, no. 20, pp. 10842–10850, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.06.005.
- [46] M. Ni, M. K. H. Leung, and D. Y. C. Leung, "Energy and exergy analysis of hydrogen production by a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer plant," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 49, no. 10, pp. 2748–2756, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2008.03.018.
- [47] J. D. Saldarriaga-Loaiza, S. D. Saldarriaga-Zuluaga, J. M. López-Lezama, F. Villada-Duque, and N. Muñoz-Galeano, "Optimal Structuring of Investments in Electricity Generation Projects in Colombia with Non-Conventional Energy Sources," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 22, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su142215123.
- [48] A. R. López *et al.*, "Solar PV generation in Colombia - A qualitative and quantitative approach to analyze the potential of solar energy market," *Renew Energy*, vol. 148, pp. 1266–1279, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2019.10.066.
- [49] EIA, "Today in energy - daily prices," 2023. Accessed: Nov. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/prices.php>
- [50] EIA, "U.S. production of petroleum and other liquids to be driven by international demand," 2023. Accessed: Nov. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.php?id=56041>
- [51] M. Cobo, C. Barraza, N. Cantillo, and M. Uribe, *Recomendaciones para el desarrollo de la economía del hidrogeno de Colombia*, First. Bogotá, Colombia, 2022.
- [52] BID, "Hoja de ruta del hidrogeno en Colombia," 2021.

[53] The World Bank, “Carbon pricing dashboard,” 2023, Accessed: Nov. 25, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://carbonpricingdashboard.worldbank.org/map_data